

The Influence of Road Bumps on Vehicle Vertical Dynamics and Vision Systems – A Validated Reference Model (Preprint)

Yannik Weber and Stratis Kanarachos

Reliability of vehicle vision systems is essential for the realisation of automated driving. Camera-based object detection and tracking systems allow the vehicle to perceive and understand its surroundings to safely navigate in and through the environment. In the development process, estimating corner and potential failure cases is a crucial step to evaluate the system's performance. Even a small deviation from known scenarios can cause system disengagements or failures. While emphasis is mostly put on the development of detection systems in simulated flat world models, the influence of vehicle dynamics is largely neglected. Road and speed bumps can have a significant impact on the tracking and position estimation process of other road participants and potentially hazardous objects.

IPG CarMaker is a vehicle simulation tool combining advanced multi-body vehicle dynamics models with a road envelope editor for the realistic recreation of road threats. Furthermore, several sensor types can be applied to the digital vehicle twin to perceive the environment.

Our experiments focus on the simulation of vehicle dynamics and a monocular camera sensor to estimate the influence of road bumps on the performance of vehicle vision systems. We validated a vehicle dynamics model for according use case and recreated a real-world camera in the simulation environment.

The validation of the dynamics and camera models

Before data was generated in IPG CarMaker, two different models were validated in the simulation: 1. The vehicle dynamics model of our vehicle and 2. The vision model of our monocular camera. For the validation process, we conducted several real-world driving trials with a research vehicle specifically equipped for the purpose. The equipment contained:

- Two acceleration sensors at different vehicle positions to record the exact vehicle chassis movement and acceleration in x-/y-/z-direction.
- A forward-facing monocular camera recording images in full-HD resolution (1920x1080 pixels) at 30 frames per second.
- A roof-mounted LiDAR sensor for the exact replication of any surrounding object in the simulation.

Beginning with the scenarios, we divided our study into three different use cases:

1. Following a moving target and hitting a road bump at 15 km/h. Parked cars serve as reference objects.
2. Following a moving target and hitting a road bump at 25 km/h. Parked cars serve as reference objects.
3. Hitting a road bump at 30 km/h without following a target. Parked cars serve as reference objects.

Regression analysis in figures one to three show the accuracy of our simulation model compared to the real-world data. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is calculated for the velocity profile as well as the distance to a reference target in the scene.

Figure 1: Regression Analysis Scenario 1 - Velocity

Figure 2: Regression Analysis Scenario 1 - Distance

In scenario 1, the RSME for the velocity is 0.62. Small deviations in the peak velocity of 1.5 km/h decrease the value. The RSME for the distance lies at 0.95.

Figure 3: Regression Analysis Scenario 2 - Velocity

Figure 4: Regression Analysis Scenario 2 - Distance

In scenario 2, the RSME for the velocity is 0.99. The RSME for the distance lies at 0.98.

Figure 5: Regression Analysis Scenario 3 - Velocity

Figure 6: Regression Analysis Scenario 3 - Distance

In scenario 1, the RSME for the velocity is 0.65. Small deviations of 1 km/h decrease the value. The RSME for the distance lies at 0.99.

The monocular camera mounted to our research vehicle has following specifications:

x-/y-/z-Position from bottom rear end	2.7/0/1.24 m
x-/y-/z- Rotation	0/4/0 deg
Field of View	120 deg
Focal Length (fx/fy)	778.4/719.03 mm
Focal Point (ox/oy)	879.52/510.61 mm

The targets in our scenarios are placed in the scenery as follows. The reference point and origin of the coordinate system is the simulation start point of our ego vehicle.

Figure 7: Target Positions Scenario 1

Target	Distance to reference point
1	87.6
2	104
3	106.67
4	126.5

Figure 8: Target Positions Scenario 2

Target	Distance to reference point
1	59.01
2	59.9
3	64.7
4	66.9
5	71.5
6	76.91

Figure 9: Target Positions Scenario 3

Target	Distance to reference point
1	38
2	45.5
3	55.5
4	63.06
5	72.31
6	73
7	77.46
8	81.5
9	85

The data set

The included data set contains three video sequences recorded with an exact copy of a realistic monocular camera. The vehicle dynamics are fully-validated for all use cases. Furthermore, we attached the recorded simulation data from a complete chassis model to analyse body movements, momentums, velocities and accelerations, as well as a full set of vehicle suspension parameters. Data is recorded at 100 Hz. All parameters can be found in the IPG CarMaker reference manual.

The data set can serve the digital development of active suspension systems to counteract chassis-movement related object detection disengagements. Another possibility would be the application of predictive controllers for the preconditioning of vehicle tracking systems. As a third opportunity, our data can be used for designing a real-time pitch angle compensation system for camera-based monocular distance estimators to serve as a redundant reference data path in safety-critical vehicle systems.

Note:

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